

Developing echolocation: distinctive patterns in the ontogeny of the tympanoperiotic complex in baleen and toothed whales (Cetacea)

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4 1 **Developing echolocation: distinctive patterns in the ontogeny of the**
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6 2 **tympanoperiotic complex in baleen and toothed whales (Cetacea)**
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32 13 **Running title:** Evo-devo Cetacea ear bones
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14 **ABSTRACT**

15 Cetaceans (baleen and toothed whales) present a unique set of adaptations for life in water. Among
16 other abilities, the two living groups can hear and produce different sound frequencies: baleen whales
17 use low frequencies primarily for communication, while toothed whales acquired the ability to
18 echolocate using high frequency sounds. Both groups exhibit modifications to the morphology of the
19 ear bones (tympanic bulla and periotic) that closely track their behaviour and ecology. While the
20 evolution of sound reception in whales is being thoroughly investigated, the changes in prenatal
21 development (ontogeny) that generate these disparate ear bone morphologies remain mostly unknown.
22 In this study, we characterize the ontogeny of the ear bones in Cetacea by looking at the progression
23 of ossification and associated changes in morphology using a combination of traditional
24 measurements and an innovative landmark-free method to quantify shape on a newly assembled 3D
25 dataset spanning the ontogeny and phylogeny of extant Cetacea. We found that the two groups of
26 Cetacea share some aspects of inner ear ontogeny, such as a common growth trajectory of the periotic.
27 However, differences in ossification, allometry and growth trajectory, particularly in the tympanic
28 bone, reflect their divergent inner ear morphology and hearing abilities.

30 **KEYWORDS**

31 Cetacea hearing-evo devo-GPSA-landmark free morphometrics

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58 INTRODUCTION

59 Drastic evolutionary shifts, such as the ones that occur during major habitat transitions, are
60 deeply connected with changes that take place during the prenatal development of the organisms.
61 Modifications during the ontogeny have the potential to give rise to new traits, and analysing
62 developmental data is of key importance to identify the role they played during the evolution of
63 groups with unique adaptations (Thewissen *et al.*, 2012; Organ *et al.*, 2015). For instance, detectable
64 changes in development of the skull have been shown to have had a deep influence in the evolution of
65 birds (e.g. Bhullar *et al.*, 2016), bats (e.g. Camacho *et al.*, 2019) and crocodiles (e.g. Morris *et al.*,
66 2019).

67 Cetacea (baleen and toothed whales – Mysticeti and Odontoceti) are one of the most
68 successful groups of tetrapods to have transitioned to an aquatic environment from a terrestrial
69 ancestor (Gatesy *et al.*, 2013; Berta & Lanzetti, 2020). Several transformations that occur during the
70 ontogeny of this group appear to directly mirror the evolutionary acquisition of their unique
71 adaptations connected to their change of habitat from their artiodactyl (even-toed ungulate) ancestor.
72 For example, the progression of telescoping – the characteristic overlapping of the bones in the
73 braincase with a progressive posterior movement of the nasal cavity (Roston & Roth, 2019) (Fig. 1) –
74 most notable in the fetuses of toothed whales (e.g. Moran *et al.*, 2011; Roston & Roth, 2019), as well
75 as the replacement of tooth germs with baleen during the ontogeny of baleen whales (e.g. Lanzetti,
76 2019), follows a similar pattern as what is observed in the fossil record (Gatesy *et al.*, 2013).

77 The drastic change from a terrestrial to an aquatic environment prompted the evolution of
78 novel sensory adaptations to enable these animals to communicate and find prey in their new
79 ecosystem (Spoor *et al.*, 2002), as it is also observed in other lineages (e.g. Neenan *et al.*, 2017;
80 Schwab *et al.*, 2020). Several unique modifications of the ear bones – a complex system of
81 interconnected elements unique to mammals, composed of the tympanic bulla, periotic, and auditory
82 ossicles (incus, stapes, malleus) (Ji *et al.*, 2009) – are present in modern toothed and baleen whales,
83 and their evolution can be traced in the fossil record starting from the earliest forms of archaic whales
84 (Archaeoceti). Extant and extinct Cetacea possess an involucrum – thickened medial process of the

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3 85 tympanic bulla that insulates the periotic from the other skull bones – and enlarged auditory ossicles
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5 86 (Luo, 1998; Nummela *et al.*, 2007; Cranford *et al.*, 2010) (Fig. 1). They also evolved a large
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7 87 mandibular foramen that houses the fat pad, a unique structure that connects the otherwise isolated ear
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9 88 bones to the jawbone (Fig. 1). All these adaptations are thought to be key to hear sounds in water
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11 89 through bone conduction (Luo, 1998; Nummela *et al.*, 2007; Gatesy *et al.*, 2013). While odontocetes
12
13 90 and mysticetes ears clearly share a common evolutionary origin, they have become adapted to hear
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15 91 and produce different sound frequencies. Baleen whales communicate among conspecific using low
16
17 92 frequency sounds (<20-200 Hz) (Fraser & Purves, 1960; Ketten, 1992; Ritsche *et al.*, 2018). Instead,
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19 93 odontocetes are among the few mammalian groups, along with bats and some rodents, to have
20
21 94 evolved to ability to echolocate, which allows them to not only communicate between each other, but
22
23 95 also to scan their surroundings for prey and obstacles, using high frequency sounds (>20-150 kHz)
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25 96 (Fraser & Purves, 1960; Ketten, 1992; Gatesy *et al.*, 2013; Ritsche *et al.*, 2018). Several studies have
26
27 97 tried to determine the evolutionary origin of these disparate hearing abilities by quantifying the
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29 98 morphology of the inner ear of Cetacea, particularly focusing on the cochlea, the spiral portion of the
30
31 99 inner ear canal where the structures responsible for sound reception reside inside the periotic
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33 100 (Solntseva, 1999; Ekdale & Racicot, 2015). The shape of the periotic and of the inner ear are also
34
35 101 correlated with the ecology and phylogeny of modern whales and dolphins, and they can also be used
36
37 102 to infer the habitat preference and evolutionary relationships of fossil taxa (Kasuya, 1973; Costeur *et*
38
39 103 *al.*, 2018; Galatius *et al.*, 2019; Park *et al.*, 2019; Viglino *et al.*, 2021). However, only a handful of
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41 104 studies have tried to characterize the evolution of the external shape the tympanic bulla or the periotic
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43 105 (Kasuya, 1973; Gutstein *et al.*, 2014; Groves *et al.*, 2021) despite the importance of these elements in
44
45 106 the evolutionary history of whales (Nummela *et al.*, 2007; Gatesy *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, the
46
47 107 ontogenetic origin of the unique features of the cetacean ear bones has been never fully investigated.
48
49 108 It has been shown that the tympanic bulla and inner ear canals mineralize and reach their adult
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51 109 morphology before birth, in contrast with what is observed in terrestrial artiodactyls and other
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53 110 mammals (Cozzi *et al.*, 2012; Cozzi *et al.*, 2015; Lancaster *et al.*, 2015; Thean *et al.*, 2016),
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55 111 demonstrating the need to investigate the prenatal development of these elements to fully understand
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57 112 the evolution of the earing adaptations seen in modern species.
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3 113 This study aims to provide the first quantitative comparison of the ontogeny of the two main
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5 114 elements of the ear bone complex, the tympanic bulla and the periotic, in Mysticeti and Odontoceti.
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7 115 Using data obtained with X-ray Computed Tomography (CT), we compare 1) the ossification
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9 116 sequences of these elements across the two extant clades, 2) reconstruct ontogenetic allometric
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11 117 changes in bone size relative to skull size (Groves *et al.*, 2021), and 3) quantify and contrast the three-
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13 118 dimensional changes in shape that take place during development using a recently described GM
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15 119 method (Pomidor *et al.*, 2016) that allows comparison of drastically different shapes without the
16
17 120 limitations of landmarks. We hypothesize that the tympanic bulla and periotic will present distinct
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19 121 ossification timings, allometric and shape growth trajectories between Mysticeti and Odontoceti given
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21 122 their diverging hearing abilities and ecology (Gatesy *et al.*, 2013; Berta & Lanzetti, 2020), and among
22
23 123 odontocetes families adapted to different habitats (Galatius *et al.*, 2019; Park *et al.*, 2019; Racicot &
24
25 124 Preucil, 2021).
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31 126 MATERIALS AND METHODS

32 127 Dataset composition

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35 128 A total of 75 specimens from 7 international museum collections, 28 Mysticeti and 47 Odontoceti,
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37 129 spanning from embryos (<2 months from conception) to adults are analysed in this study for the
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39 130 tympanic bulla. As the periotic starts ossifying in later stages of gestation (Moran *et al.*, 2011;
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41 131 Lanzetti, 2019), only 46 of these specimens could be used for analyses of this element. Specimens
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43 132 were binned into embryos or early fetuses (estimated age <50% total gestational length, n = 45), late
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45 133 fetuses (>50% total gestational length, n = 19), and postnatal specimens (neonates, juveniles and
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47 134 adults, n = 11). Further details on specimens and aging estimates are provided in the Supporting
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49 135 Information (Supplemental Methods; Table S1).
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52 136 This unparalleled dataset has representatives of all four living mysticetes families and of five
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54 137 of the 10 extant families of odontocetes. Comparative analyses at taxon level were conducted only on
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56 138 the four taxa with the most complete ontogenetic sampling: minke whales (*Balaenoptera*
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58 139 *acutorostrata* and *B. bonaerensis*) and fin whale (*B. physalus*) for Mysticeti, and harbour porpoise
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3 140 (*Phocoena phocoena*) and pantropical spotted dolphin (*Stenella attenuata*) for Odontoceti. The minke
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5 141 and fin whales are pooled for the analysis of the periotic as one taxon. All other analyses are
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7 142 conducted at groups level (Mysticeti and Odontoceti) using the entire datasets. Intraspecific variation
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9 143 is negligible in cetacean ear bones (Martins *et al.*, 2020), so we consider that the number of samples
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11 144 for each developmental stages per species is appropriate for this study.

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14 145 Fluid preserved and disarticulated osteological specimens have been digitized using X-ray CT
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16 146 and diffusible iodine-based contrast-enhanced X-ray CT (diceCT) (Lanzetti & Ekdale, 2021). All CT
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18 147 datasets were prepared in ImageJ (Schneider *et al.*, 2012), and the 3D surfaces were reconstructed in
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20 148 Avizo 2020.3 (FEI, 2021). The surfaces were then processed in Geomagic Wrap 2017 (3D Systems
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22 149 Inc., 2017). Further details on CT imaging and surface processing are provided in the Supporting
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24 150 Information (Supplemental Methods; Table S2).

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27 28 152 Measurements and landmark-free quantification of 3D shape

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30 153 To assess changes in size of the tympanic bulla and periotic relative to skull size (size
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32 154 allometry), measurements of length and width of each ear bone element and skull bizygomatic width
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34 155 (BZW) were taken in Meshlab 2020.07 (Cignoni *et al.*, 2008) following (Groves *et al.*, 2021) for the
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36 156 tympanic bulla and BZW and (Kasuya, 1973) for the periotic (Supporting Information, Figure S1).

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39 157 To quantify shape variation in each of the two datasets, surfaces were scored using a
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41 158 landmark-free method, Generalized Procrustes Surface Analysis or GPSA (Pomidor *et al.*, 2016). All
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43 159 surfaces are superimposed to a reference (prototype) to find the nearest corresponding neighbour of
44
45 160 each pseudolandmark and calculate their location relative to the prototype, similar to Generalized
46
47 161 Procrustes Analysis (GPA) of standard landmarks. These pseudolandmarks (aligned points)
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49 162 correspond largely to each of the surface triangles in a mesh and are placed algorithmically, therefore
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51 163 removing the need of identifying standard homologous points, and can be used for all standard
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53 164 analyses of shape variation. This landmark-free approach is particularly useful for quantifying the
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55 165 shapes in heterogenous ontogenetic series, as not all parts of the bone elements are present from the
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57 166 start of ossification, and it would only be possible to place at most a few homologous landmarks on all

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3 167 specimens, highly underrepresenting the complexity of more mature individuals. Full details of the
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5 168 GPSA method are provided in the Supporting Information (Supplemental Methods).

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7 169 The GPSA analyses were performed using the latest version of the stand-alone Java
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9 170 application listed in the original publication (Pomidor *et al.*, 2016). All the PLY files used in GPSA
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11 171 analyses, including the prototype, as well as the all the text outputs from the GPSA software are
12
13 172 available on Dryad Digital Repository (<https://doi.org/10.6086/D1R69C>).

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17 174 Ossification sequence and size allometry

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20 175 Ossification sequence data was compared qualitatively by plotting ossification progression for the
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22 176 two elements on growth curves for the four best sampled taxa (minke whales, fin whales, harbour
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24 177 porpoise, pantropical spotted dolphin), estimated with data available in the literature (Laws, 1959;
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26 178 Lanzetti *et al.*, 2020), following the methodology described in Lanzetti *et al.* (2020). All statistical
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28 179 analysis were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2021) and results visualized using *ggplot2* (Wickham,
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30 180 2016).

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33 181 Ontogenetic allometric trajectories describing growth in element size relative to skull growth,
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35 182 measured as the BZW, were calculated as linear regressions (*lm* function from the base *stat* package)
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37 183 of the log-transformed measurements for the entire dataset. We then tested for significant differences
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39 184 in allometry between Mysticeti and Odontoceti, with models assessing both element size
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41 185 (combination) and growth rate (interaction) against a null model with no taxonomic grouping. Models
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43 186 were compared using the *anova* function (base *stat* package) and assessing model fit with AICc scores
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45 187 calculated with the *AICcmodavg* package (Mazerolle, 2020).

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48 49 189 Quantitative analyses of 3D shape

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51 190 Shape data (aligned points coordinates) from the GPSA for the tympanic bulla and periotic were
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53 191 imported separately in R along with covariates (group, growth category, tympanic bulla and periotic
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55 192 length measurement), and a PCA on the entire dataset was performed using the *gm.prcomp* function in
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57 193 *geomorph* (Baken *et al.*, 2021). The PCOORD scores and values were also imported in R and plotted
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59 194 to compare those results with the PCA (Supporting Information, Fig. S2–S3, Table S4–S5). Linear

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3 195 regressions for each of the first two components versus size, group and growth category were
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5 196 performed using the *lm* function to assess how these factors relate to the distribution of data in the
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7 197 PCA plot. All the PC scores for the four best sampled taxa mentioned above were selected from the
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9 198 PCA to perform a shape allometry analysis. This is used to identify if taxonomic grouping has an
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11 199 impact on shape growth relative to size, summarized as the log-transformed length of the element.
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13 200 Similar to the size allometry analysis, the null model with no group effect was tested against a
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15 201 combination model, where grouping influences general shape but not on the rate of change, and
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17 202 interaction model, where grouping has effect on both overall shape and rate of growth. This analysis
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19 203 was conducted using *procD.lm*, with significant differences in models and pairwise differences in
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21 204 growth rate and direction between each pair of taxa assessed with ANOVA and *RRPP* (Collyer &
22
23 205 Adams, 2021). Lastly, a trajectory analysis (*trajectory.analysis* function) was performed to highlight
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25 206 differences in the path of shape growth between Mysticeti and Odontoceti. This analysis was
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27 207 conducted using shape data for the entire dataset, as it requires even sampling of ontogenetic stages.
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29 208 The raw data and code used to construct all the plots and conduct the statistical analysis are available
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31 209 on GitHub (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5534706>).
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211 RESULTS

212 Ossification sequence

213 Three main ossification stages were identified for both elements based on previous literature
214 (Kuzmin, 1976; Luo, 1998; Moran *et al.*, 2011; Hampe *et al.*, 2015; Lanzetti, 2019) and also plotted
215 on growth curves of selected taxa (Fig. 2). The three stages can be described as follows: 1) element
216 visible, 2) element shape recognizable with some processes missing, 3) element completely ossified
217 (Fig. 2A). The tympanic bulla in stage 1 of ossification presents as a U-shaped or sigmoid shaped
218 bone, very similar in both Mysticeti and Odontoceti. The periotic only has the central cochlear portion
219 ossified in both groups. At stage 2, the progression of ossification appears overall similar in the two
220 groups, although some differences can be found in the periotic. The tympanic cavity, sigmoid process
221 and accessory ossicle are ossified, but the involucrum and the posterior process are not yet present in
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3 222 the tympanic bulla. For the periotic, the internal acoustic meatus and the vestibular aqueduct appear
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5 223 better defined than in the first stage, but in baleen whales the ossification of the posterior process
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7 224 seems to proceed faster than the anterior process, while both processes appear to grow at more similar
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9 225 rates in toothed whales. At stage 3 all processes are completely ossified and the difference in shape
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11 226 between the two groups is much more marked, as it is expected in postnatal specimens (Ekdale, 2016;
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13 227 Mourlam & Orliac, 2017).

15 228 By plotting the occurrence of these three events for each element on the growth curve of the
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17 229 four best sampled taxa in the dataset, it is clear that tympanic bulla ossification events occur before
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19 230 those of the periotic (Fig. 2B). The tympanic bulla is visible from the early stages of the gestation in
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21 231 odontocetes, possibly from the embryonic period in the dolphin as shown in Moran *et al.* (2011).
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23 232 Though we do not have direct evidence for this in the dataset for this species, the tympanic bulla is
24
25 233 already visible in most embryos of sperm whale that we examined. In baleen whales, this element is
26
27 234 visible from about 30% of the gestation, but it is possible it is present from earlier stages as suggested
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29 235 by previous work on the humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) (Lanzetti *et al.*, 2020). The
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31 236 progression of ossification is then rapid, with large parts of the bone ossified (stage 2) by 30-50% of
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33 237 gestation in both groups. Then, the tympanic bulla appears to continue ossify at a fast rate in the
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35 238 porpoise and in the fin whale, reaching complete ossification around 50-60% of the gestation, while
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37 239 this process seems slower in the dolphin and in minke whales, where it only reaches stage 3 around
38
39 240 70% of the gestation. The periotic starts ossifying later in both toothed and baleen whales, likely not
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41 241 before 30% of the gestation, which was also noted for other species (Kuzmin, 1976; Lanzetti *et al.*,
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43 242 2020). Then ossification proceeds quickly between stage 1 and 2, as observed for the tympanic bulla,
44
45 243 with this element being visibly more ossified by 40% of the gestation, except for the minke whales,
46
47 244 where this shift seems to occur around 60%. Complete ossification of the periotic occurs at different
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49 245 times among taxa as observed for the tympanic bulla. In the fin whale, while we do not have a
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51 246 specimen with a periotic at stage 3 in the dataset, we estimate based on the timing of complete
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53 247 ossification of the tympanic bulla that it occurs in line with the porpoise, which maintains an earlier
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55 248 complete ossification of this element, occurring around 60% of the gestation. In the minke whales and
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3 249 in the dolphin, the complete ossification of the periotic occurs later around 80% of the gestation, in
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5 250 line with what was observed for the tympanic bulla.

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9 252 Size allometry

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11 253 All four size measurements (bulla length, bulla width, periotic length, periotic width) showed a
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13 254 positive allometric relationship with skull size (Supporting Information, Fig. S4, Table S5). For bulla
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15 255 length, bulla width and periotic length, the interaction model is supported over the null and
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17 256 combination models (Table 1). While the rate of growth is significantly different between the two
18
19 257 groups for all these three measurements, size difference is not (Table 1). This is likely due to the
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21 258 overall small size of the ear bones, which is partially obscured by the log transformation, and also by
22
23 259 the lack of adult mysticetes in the dataset. For periotic width, while the interaction model was again
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25 260 preferred, it was not significantly different from the combination model. This implies that there is
26
27 261 only a marginal difference in growth rate between the groups, with overall differences in size driving
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29 262 the relationship.

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33 264 Quantitative analyses of 3D shape

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35 265 The distribution of specimens on the first two PC axes for each element clearly shows that the
36
37 266 tympanic bulla and periotic do not have similar patterns of shape variation. The distribution in the
38
39 267 tympanic bulla dataset is influenced by ontogenetic stage while taxonomic grouping appears to be
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41 268 driving the variation in the periotic. Further details on the PCA plots can be found in the Supporting
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43 269 Information (Supplemental Methods; Fig. S5; Table S3–S4).

44
45 270 To quantify shape allometry through ontogeny, we then subsetted our dataset to the PC scores
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47 271 for the four best sampled taxa. We found a consistent positive allometric relationship between size of
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49 272 the element and shape change during ontogeny, with distinct patterns distinguishing baleen and
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51 273 toothed whales (Fig. 3). For both the tympanic bulla and periotic, there is a significant effect of
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53 274 taxonomic grouping not only on the overall shape but also on the rate of shape change during growth,
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55 275 with the interaction model being better supported than the null and combination models (Supporting
56
57 276 Information, Table S6). Pairwise comparisons demonstrate that there is a significant difference in

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2
3 277 overall growth rate of the tympanic bulla between all pairs of taxa (distance of slopes), but the
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5 278 difference in direction of growth is not significantly different between the two mysticetes (angles of
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7 279 slopes) (Fig. 3A) (Arribart *et al.*, 2018; Costeur *et al.*, 2018; Galatius *et al.*, 2019). In the periotic (Fig.
8
9 280 3B), the two mysticetes are treated as one taxon due to uneven sampling (see Materials and Methods
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11 281 section). This element is believed to be very closely associated with hearing abilities, as it houses the
12
13 282 inner ear canals (Fraser & Purves, 1960; Gutstein *et al.*, 2014), and in fact we recover a significant
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15 283 difference in the rate and direction of growth between mysticetes and each of the two odontocetes.
16
17 284 Though, the dolphin and the porpoise were not significantly different (Supporting Information, Table
18
19 285 S6), despite their distinct habitat and phylogenetic position (Arribart *et al.*, 2018; Galatius *et al.*,
20
21 286 2019), and in direct contrast with the results for the tympanic bulla.
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23

24 287 We further compared ontogenetic shape change between mysticetes and odontocetes using a
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26 288 trajectory analysis on the entire dataset. The plotted trajectories of the two elements are markedly
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28 289 different (Fig. 4). In the case of the tympanic bulla (Fig. 4A), in both groups a higher proportion of
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30 290 shape change seems to occur between early and late fetal stages, with the two trajectories having an
31
32 291 overall similar shape. This is confirmed by the quantitative comparison of the two paths, where
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34 292 trajectory direction, but not length or shape, was significantly different (Supporting Information,
35
36 293 Table S7). The trajectories recovered for the periotic are very different and show a more marked
37
38 294 divergence between the two groups (Fig. 4B), running perpendicular to each other but both drawing a
39
40 295 linear path. In Mysticeti, a greater portion of shape change occurring from the late fetal to the
41
42 296 postnatal stage. The path of Odontoceti starts from same area of the morphospace where the late fetal
43
44 297 Mysticeti are positioned, with the greatest proportion of shape change instead taking place between
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46 298 early and late fetal stages. Quantitative analysis corroborates these observations, with the paths
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48 299 showing a significant difference in length, with Mysticeti being the longer path, and in direction, but
49
50 300 not shape (Supporting Information, Table S7).
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301 **DISCUSSION**

302 Complex evolutionary transitions, such as the shift from land to water, can be traced through
303 the ontogeny of taxa (Thewissen *et al.*, 2012; Organ *et al.*, 2015; Camacho *et al.*, 2019). Prenatal
304 development of closely related species usually possesses many shared characteristics derived from
305 their common ancestors, but several small key differences are recognizable that are connected to their
306 unique morphologies and adaptations (Bhullar *et al.*, 2016; Camacho *et al.*, 2019; Morris *et al.*, 2019).
307 The ontogeny of the tympanoperiotic complex in Cetacea clearly shows how both shared and
308 diverging subtle changes in development are responsible for allowing major evolutionary transitions
309 and distinct ecological adaptations that characterize modern baleen and toothed whales (Gatesy *et al.*,
310 2013; Berta & Lanzetti, 2020). Their common ancestry and initial changes that occurred in their fossil
311 relatives to adapt to life in water are visible in the many aspects shared by the two groups, such as
312 shared allometric trend in both elements and common growth trajectory in the tympanic bulla.
313 However, the functional differences in their current hearing abilities (e.g. Ekdale, 2016; Park *et al.*,
314 2019) also start appearing from early in their development, as exemplified by the growth trajectory of
315 the periotic.

317 Development of shared traits for underwater hearing

318 The tympanic bulla presents several adaptations, such as the involucrum, that characterize
319 Cetacea from their earliest recognized fossil representatives and are likely key features to allow
320 hearing in water (Luo, 1998; Nummela *et al.*, 2007). The need to develop these unique structures
321 likely constrains the ontogeny of this element in modern taxa. The earlier ossification of this element
322 in both Mysticeti and Odontoceti relative to the periotic is a feature common in mammals (Koyabu *et*
323 *al.*, 2014) that was also found in previous studies gestation (e.g. Moran *et al.*, 2011; Lanzetti, 2019),
324 although the rapid pace of ossification, which is completed before birth, is unique to Cetacea (Cozzi *et*
325 *al.*, 2012; Cozzi *et al.*, 2015). Shape changes during ontogeny and the developmental trajectory of the
326 tympanic bulla do not appear to be influenced by taxonomic grouping, as the growth paths and
327 distribution of variation are similar between the two. Positive allometry of size and shape is also

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3 328 shared by baleen and toothed whales for both elements. This is of particular interest for the periotic, as
4
5 329 it has been shown that the internal ear canals hosted in the cochlear portion of this bone have a
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7 330 negative allometric relationship with skull size in both toothed whales (Thean *et al.*, 2016) and
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9 331 ruminants (Costeur *et al.*, 2017). Other parts of the skull, particularly the rostrum, have been found to
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11 332 have positive size allometry in prenatal and postnatal ontogeny for mysticetes and odontocetes
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13 333 (Gol'din, 2007; Nakamura *et al.*, 2012). While the allometry of periotic length showed different rates
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15 334 of growth between the two groups, this was not the case for periotic width, where the two groups
16
17 335 mostly differed in overall size. The width of the periotic spans the aperture of the internal acoustic
18
19 336 meatus and can be considered a proxy for size of the inner ear canals. These are significantly different
20
21 337 in morphology between Mysticeti and Odontoceti due to their diverging hearing abilities (Ekdale &
22
23 338 Racicot, 2015), and it might be expected to present different allometric trajectories between the two
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25 339 groups. The discrepancy in size but not in rate observed in this analysis might be due to the higher
26
27 340 functional constraints imposed by underwater hearing and movement (Spoor *et al.*, 2002) that are
28
29 341 likely to control the development of the central part of the bone, in combination with the effect of the
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31 342 negative allometric relationship between the size of the inner ear canals and the skull (Thean *et al.*,
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33 343 2016).
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39 Accelerated growth in baleen whales

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41 346 Studies investigating differences in prenatal development in Cetacea consistently found that
42
43 347 Mysticeti present an overall accelerated development relative to Odontoceti, both in body size and in
44
45 348 head size and shape, likely due to their larger size and relatively longer rostrum (Armfield *et al.*,
46
47 349 2011; Berta & Lanzetti, 2020; Lanzetti *et al.*, 2020). Baleen whales also have a much larger tympanic
48
49 350 bullae relative to toothed whales, as underscored by evolutionary allometry studies (Groves *et al.*,
50
51 351 2021). This difference is recovered in our shape and size ontogenetic allometry analyses. The two
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53 352 groups present different rates of growth, with mysticetes having a faster growth rate for both the
54
55 353 relative size and the shape of the element compared to odontocetes. Mysticeti are represented in our
56
57 354 dataset mostly by specimens of rorqual whales (Balaenopteridae), which possess a distinctive
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59 355 tympanic bulla morphology even among baleen whales (Yamato & Pyenson, 2015). While this is
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3 356 unlikely to affect our overall results, it might be connected to the highly divergent allometric growth
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5 357 rate recovered for shape in particular, and future research should include more samples to investigate
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7 358 differences among mysticetes families. The ontogeny of the periotic shows more profound differences
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9 359 between Mysticeti and Odontoceti, owing to their divergent hearing adaptations that are characterized
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11 360 by unique inner ear morphology (Ekdale & Racicot, 2015; Ekdale, 2016). The progression of
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13 361 ossification in this element, as well as shape variation across ontogeny and growth trajectories, are
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15 362 markedly different between the two groups, which display differentiated shapes from early in their
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17 363 development. Similarly, the rate of growth of periotic shape differs significantly between the two
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19 364 groups, with mysticetes again showing a faster rate of development.
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23 24 366 Distinct allometric patterns among toothed whales

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26 367 In the shape allometry analysis, we were able to investigate differences between two odontocetes
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28 368 families (pantropical spotted dolphin, Delphinidae, and harbour porpoise, Phocoenidae). They have
29
30 369 different acoustic abilities due to their different habitats and sociality (Arribart *et al.*, 2018; Galatius *et*
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32 370 *al.*, 2019), and they also differ by in body and skull size (Read, 1999; Perrin, 2001). In fact, rate of
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34 371 change in shape of the tympanic bulla was found to be significantly different between the two. This
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36 372 although was not the case for the periotic, despite their differences well described in the adults
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38 373 (Kasuya, 1973; Gutstein *et al.*, 2014). This result is likely due to the constraints imposed on inner ear
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40 374 and in turn periotic shape by the evolution of echolocation. Inner ear morphology connected to
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42 375 echolocating ability is so distinctive that it has been recognised to have evolved convergently in
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44 376 different groups of extinct and extant toothed whales (Park *et al.*, 2019; Racicot *et al.*, 2019). The
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46 377 low-frequency hearing of baleen whales, on the other hand, is likely to reflect the ancestral hearing
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48 378 abilities of Cetacea and it is possible that these taxa still retain some ancestral developmental
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50 379 characteristics that are lost in toothed whales. While most studies on the evolution of hearing in
51
52 380 Odontoceti focus on the periotic and internal canals (e.g. Mourlam & Orliac, 2017; Viglino *et al.*,
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54 381 2021), this result shows that the shape and particularly the ontogeny of the tympanic bulla might
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56 382 preserve important information to understand how different groups evolved their distinct modes of
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58 383 echolocation suited for their specific ecology.
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3 384 **CONCLUSION**
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5 385 Our results show that prenatal development of the ear bones in baleen and toothed whales
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7 386 retains aspects of their common evolutionary history while also explaining their divergent
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9 387 morphologies connected to their different hearing abilities, highlighting the importance of
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11 388 incorporating ontogenetic data in evolutionary studies. Recognizing what parts of the tympanoperiotic
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13 389 complex are more or less shared by the two groups based on their prenatal development can help
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15 390 assess the homology of traits and inform both the interpretation of fossil morphologies and the
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17 391 ongoing debate on the ancestral hearing abilities of extinct groups (e.g. Ekdale & Racicot, 2015;
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19 392 Mourlam & Orliac, 2017). Of particular interest for future studies are the differences in growth for the
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21 393 tympanic bulla observed between families of toothed whales.
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24 394 The use of CT imaging has allowed to greatly increase our knowledge of the internal anatomy
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26 395 of Cetacea (Racicot, 2021). This study shows that it is possible to successfully apply a landmark-free
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28 396 approach (GPSA) to these data to conduct quantitative analyses, which produced results consistent
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30 397 with both previous studies and with our measurement analysis. The PCOORD and PCA results were
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32 398 also found to be equivalent, supporting comparability of this approach to traditional landmark studies.
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34 399 In the future, finer scale studies of evolutionary changes in the morphology of the tympanic bulla in
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36 400 extant and extant odontocetes using GPSA as well as other similar approaches (e.g. Boyer *et al.*,
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38 401 2015) might shed new light on the evolution of echolocation in this group. Expanding the dataset to
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40 402 include a more diverse group of Cetacea with complete ontogenetic sequences for multiple families of
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42 403 Mysticeti and Odontoceti, as well as closely related terrestrial artiodactyls, will help improve the
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44 404 robustness of the findings and elucidate how differences in development contribute to the evolution of
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46 405 ecological adaptations in disparate species.
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11 571

14 572 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

16 573 The data underlying this article are available in Dryad Digital Repository at
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18 574 <https://doi.org/10.6086/D1R69C> (preview link for peer review:
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20 575 <https://datadryad.org/stash/share/P6YMy3QspoUdNIIyy5A9DV5ojdryerS1Bb1GIRO4uwE>) and the
21
22 576 code is available on Github and archived on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5534706>.
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27 578 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

29 579 **Supplemental Methods:** Document containing supplemental information on the methods used for
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31 580 data collection, preparation, GPSA analyses and comparison between PCOORD and PCA results
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33 581 **Figure S1:** Measurements of periotic (A), tympanic bulla (B) and skull (C) used in the size allometry
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35 582 analysis, illustrated with 3D rendering of the skull and ear bones of *Phoca3* (adult, NHMUK2021.2,
36
37 583 *Phocoena phocoena*, Odontoceti). Length of ear bone element in green, width in violet (A and B).
38
39 584 Bizygomatic width of skull (BZW) in black dashed line (C). Box on the skull indicates the position of
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41 585 the right ear bone complex that was used in the analyses. Periotic (light grey) is in dorsal view (A),
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43 586 tympanic bulla (dark grey) and skull (light yellow) in ventral view (B and C), models not to scale. For
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45 587 immature specimens, greatest length and width of the bone were used, measured with the elements
46
47 588 oriented in the same way as illustrated here. Measurements chosen following Kasuya (1973) and
48
49 589 Groves et al. (2021).
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52 590 **Figure S2:** Comparison of PCA plot (A) and PCOORD plot (B) of the first two components for the
53
54 591 tympanic bulla dataset. All specimens are labelled on the plots using the codes listed in the Supporting
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56 592 Information (Table S1). PCA plot same as in the Supporting Information, Fig. S5A. Legends apply to
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58 593 both plots.
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3 594 **Figure S3:** Comparison of PCA plot (A) and PCOORD plot (B) of the first two components for the
4
5 595 periotic dataset. All specimens are labelled on the plots using the codes listed in the Supporting
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7 596 Information (Table S1). PCA plot same as in the Supporting Information, Fig. S5B. Legends apply to
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9 597 both plots.

11 598 **Figure S4:** Allometric trajectories of ear bone size growth relative to skull growth in Mysticeti and
12
13 599 Odontoceti. Size of the ear bone elements is summarized as tympanic bulla (bulla) and periotic length
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15 600 (A and C) and width (B and D); skull size is summarized as bizygomatic width (BZW).
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17 601 Measurements illustrated in the Supporting Information (Fig. S1). All measurements are log-
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19 602 transformed. Asterisks indicate significance of interaction portion of model for panels A, B and C,
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21 603 where a significant difference between the slopes of the two groups was found, and the significance of
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23 604 the combination portion in panel D, where only a difference in intercept was found (see Table 1;
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25 605 Supporting Information, Table S5). Significance codes: ‘***’ $p < 0.001$, ‘**’ $p < 0.01$, ‘*’ $p < 0.5$.
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27 606 Colours, line type and silhouettes as in Fig. 2 and Fig. 4.

30 607 **Figure S5:** PCA plots for 3D shape data of the tympanic bulla (A) and periotic (B) datasets. All
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32 608 specimens are represented in the plots. Colours, lines, and symbols legends apply to both plots.
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34 609 Coloured hulls delimit morphospace of different growth categories, grey solid line delimits Mysticeti
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36 610 morphospace, dashed Odontoceti.

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39 611 **Table S1:** List of specimens analysed in the study. This table includes specimens’ codes used to refer
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41 612 to specimens in the figures and captions, as well as file numbering used for GPSA analysis, museum
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43 613 accession number, taxonomic information, total length and age estimate, growth category assignment,
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45 614 ossification status and measurements of bizygomatic width, bulla and periotic, as well as reference to
46
47 615 who provided the data. Additional notes are provided in a separate sheet.

49 616 **Table S2:** CT acquisition details for specimens used in this study. Facility, CT system model used
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51 617 and details on image acquisition (kV, mA, slice thickness, voxel size, filtration, number of
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53 618 projections, exposure time, number of images, output format for images) are included when possible.
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55 619 MorphoSource links are provided for images of specimens already available on the repository.
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57 620 Additional notes are provided in a separate sheet.

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3 621 **Table S3:** List of components/axes values, singular and cumulative proportion of variance for the
4
5 622 PCA and PCOORD analysis of the tympanic bulla and periotic datasets.

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7 623 **Table S4.** Results of ANOVA analyses of the first two components of the PCA and PCOORD
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9 624 analysis with size (log-length of element), taxonomic groups, and growth category as independent
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11 625 variables. Significant values in bold.

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13 626 **Table S5.** Full results size allometry analysis. For each of the four measurements, details on the three
14
15 627 tested models (no group difference, differ intercept or combination and different slopes or interaction)
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17 628 are reported, along with model comparison as ANOVA table and AICc analysis for model selection.
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19 629 Skull size (BZW_log) and each measurement of the two elements were analysed after log-
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21 630 transformation. Significant values in bold, in AICc models listed from lowest to highest scores.

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23 631 **Table S6.** Full results shape allometry analysis. For each of the two elements, details on the three
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25 632 tested models (no difference between taxa, differ intercept or combination and different slopes or
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27 633 interaction) are reported, along with model comparison as an ANOVA table. As for both elements the
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29 634 model with different slopes was significantly different, pairwise analyses of absolute slope distance
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31 635 and angle between slopes for each taxon pair was conducted. Size is the log-length of the element.
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33 636 Taxa are listed with scientific names (*B. bonaerensis* – minke whales, *B. physalus* – fin whale, *P.*
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35 637 *phocoena* – harbour porpoise, *S. attenuata* – pantropical spotted dolphin). The fin whale was not
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37 638 considered as a separate taxon for analysis of the periotic therefore those comparisons are not
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39 639 available. P-values for pairwise differences calculated with 1000 permutations. Significant values in
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41 640 bold.

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43 641 **Table S7.** Full results of trajectory analysis comparing trajectory of shape growth between Mysticeti
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45 642 and Odontoceti. Length, angle and shape of trajectories summarized, including total length of path for
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47 643 each of the two groups. P-values calculated with 500 permutations. Significant p-values in bold.
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3 644 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**
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5 645 **Figure 1.** Schematic representation of the most distinctive features of the skull and ear bones of
6
7 646 Cetacea. The skull of the neonate goral (*Naemorhedus* sp., Bovidae, Artiodactyla) on the left has an
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9 647 enlarged orbit and anterior nasal passage compared to an adult harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*,
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11 648 Odontoceti, Cetacea) on the right. The tympanic bulla of the goral lacks the involucrum and the
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13 649 mandibular foramen (shaded area) is small, while the porpoise presents the thickened involucrum
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15 650 (dotted-dashed line), enlarged auditory ossicles (in dashed line area, not visible), and an enlarged
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17 651 mandibular foramen (shaded area). Skull in light yellow, tympanic bulla in dark grey and periotic in
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19 652 light grey, lateral view, not to scale. Right mandibular ramus removed in the lower figures. Goral
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21 653 skull reconstructed using CT images provided by Haley O'Brien, silhouettes by AL.

22 654 **Figure 2.** Representative 3D shapes of tympanic bulla and periotic at the three stages of their
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24 655 development (A) and plot of these developmental events on the growth curves of selected taxa (B).
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26 656 Italicized numbers indicate the specimen chosen to represent the stage, as reported in the electronic
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28 657 supplementary materials, table S1. Ear bones in dorsal view, not to scale, coloured as taxonomic
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30 658 groups (light green=Mysticeti, violet=Odontoceti). Abbreviations: ao, accessory ossicle, app, anterior
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32 659 process of the periotic, cp, cochlear portion, iam, internal auditory meatus, in, involucrum, ppb,
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34 660 posterior process of the tympanic bulla, ppp, posterior process of the periotic, sp, sigmoid process, tc,
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36 661 tympanic cavity, va, vestibular aqueduct. Gestational age expressed as percentage of progression
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38 662 relative to total gestation time to account for different gestational length among taxa (Lanzetti *et al.*,
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40 663 2020). Age of ossification events based on total length of specimens, stage 1 of tympanic bulla for the
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42 664 pantropical spotted dolphin placed according to Moran *et al.* (2011) (striped fill), stage 3 of periotic
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44 665 for the fin whale estimated based on other species (shaded fill and dashed outline). Silhouettes by AL.

45 666 **Figure 3.** Allometry of shape (regression score derived from PC scores) relative to size (log-
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47 667 transformed length of element) by taxon for the tympanic bulla (A) and periotic (B). Only the four
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49 668 selected taxa represented on the plots are included in the analysis. Asterisks on the y-axis label
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51 669 indicate significance of interaction between size and taxon ($p=0.001$ for tympanic bulla, $p=0.004$ for
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53 670 periotic). Legend applies to both plots. Colour and silhouettes for taxa as in Fig. 2.
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3 671 **Figure 4.** Trajectories of shape change during ontogeny for Mysticeti and Odontoceti for the
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5 672 tympanic bulla (A) and periotic (B) in the entire dataset. Arrows indicate direction of growth, last
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7 673 stage (postnatal) labelled for reference. Transparency follows growth progression, from more
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9 674 transparent (early fetus) to less (postnatal). Silhouettes by AL.

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For Peer Review

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the most distinctive features of the skull and ear bones of Cetacea. The skull of the neonate goral (*Naemorhedus* sp., Bovidae, Artiodactyla) on the left has an enlarged orbit and anterior nasal passage compared to an adult harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*, Odontoceti, Cetacea) on the right. The tympanic bulla of the goral lacks the involucrum and the mandibular foramen (shaded area) is small, while the porpoise presents the thickened involucrum (dotted-dashed line), enlarged auditory ossicles (in dashed line area, not visible), and an enlarged mandibular foramen (shaded area). Skull in light yellow, tympanic bulla in dark grey and periotic in light grey, lateral view, not to scale. Right mandibular ramus removed in the lower figures. Goral skull reconstructed using CT images provided by Haley O'Brien, silhouettes by AL.

245x147mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Figure 2. Representative 3D shapes of tympanic bulla and periotic at the three stages of their development (A) and plot of these developmental events on the growth curves of selected taxa (B).

Italicized numbers indicate the specimen chosen to represent the stage, as reported in the electronic supplementary materials, table S1. Ear bones in dorsal view, not to scale, coloured as taxonomic groups (light green=Mysticeti, violet=Odontoceti). Abbreviations: ao, accessory ossicle, app, anterior process of the periotic, cp, cochlear portion, iam, internal auditory meatus, in, involocrum, ppb, posterior process of the tympanic bulla, ppp, posterior process of the periotic, sp, sigmoid process, tc, tympanic cavity, va, vestibular aqueduct. Gestational age expressed as percentage of progression relative to total gestation time to account for different gestational length among taxa (Lanzetti et al., 2020). Age of ossification events based on total length of specimens, stage 1 of tympanic bulla for the pantropical spotted dolphin placed according to Moran et al. (2011) (striped fill), stage 3 of periotic for the fin whale estimated based on other species (shaded fill and dashed outline). Silhouettes by AL.

255x195mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Figure 3. Allometry of shape (regression score derived from PC scores) relative to size (log-transformed length of element) by taxon for the tympanic bulla (A) and periotic (B). Only the four selected taxa represented on the plots are included in the analysis. Asterisks on the y-axis label indicate significance of interaction between size and taxon ($p= 0.001$ for tympanic bulla, $p=0.004$ for periotic). Legend applies to both plots. Colour and silhouettes for taxa as in Fig. 2.

285x100mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Figure 4. Trajectories of shape change during ontogeny for Mysticeti and Odontoceti for the tympanic bulla (A) and periotic (B) in the entire dataset. Arrows indicate direction of growth, last stage (postnatal) labelled for reference. Transparency follows growth progression, from more transparent (early fetus) to less (postnatal). Silhouettes by AL.

282x109mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Table 1. Summary of results for size allometry model comparison for the four measurements. P-values relative to null model with no taxonomic grouping considered. Significant p-values and lowest AICc scores in bold. See Materials and Methods section for explanation of the models, and Supporting Information, Table S5 for full results.

	<i>Tympanic bulla length</i>		<i>Tympanic bulla width</i>		<i>Periotic length</i>		<i>Periotic width</i>	
	p-value	AICc score	p-value	AICc score	p-value	AICc score	p-value	AICc score
null	<i>ref</i>	-7.38	<i>ref</i>	-1.49	<i>ref</i>	12.78	<i>ref</i>	-24.91
combination	0.926	-5.15	0.516	0.32	0.096	12.52	5.499E-07	-48.46
interaction	0.013	-9.36	0.028	-2.49	0.013	8.22	0.053	-50.08